

APPRAISAL OF PRINCIPALS' MANAGERIAL PRACTICES FOR TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

Carol Obiageli Ezeugborⁱ,

Ogechukwu Nwakaego Emere

Department of Educational Management and Policy,
Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Nigeria

Abstract:

The study appraised principals' managerial practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study was 6,652 principals and teachers of public secondary schools in Anambra State, consisting of the entire 256 principals and 6,396 teachers in the State. A sample of 1,996 principals and teachers were drawn from the population through proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Data was collected using a questionnaire of 16 items which was validated by three experts from the faculty of education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliability co-efficient which yielded 0.87 and 0.73, summing it up to an overall reliability co-efficient of 0.80 which was considered adequate for the study. Data analysis was done using mean for answering the research questions. The z-test was adopted to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that principals adopted managerial practices which include instructional leadership practices and supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness. It was also found out that there was a significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on their managerial practices. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that principals should intensify efforts in their supervisory roles to ensure that the objectives of secondary education could be regularly achieved.

ⁱ Correspondence: email co.ezeugbor@unizik.edu.ng

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1. Introduction

The broad goals of the secondary education as enunciated in the National Policy on Education are to prepare the individuals for (a) useful living within the society, and (b) for higher education (FRN, 2013). This policy stipulation calls for proper management of secondary education through effective leadership of the principles whose managerial practices also contribute towards teacher effectiveness. This apparently promotes quality instructional delivery in the secondary schools.

Today, the principal is saddled with a lot of problems and distractions that most often culminate in his/her inability to cope with overwhelming managerial challenges that stir him on the face. The concomitant effect of this probably lies in the failure of both the teachers and students to perform effectively with minimal supervision. Since management is an integral part of any organization in which effective leadership is directed towards the achievement of predetermined goals, the onus lies on the principals to take the bull by the horn and shun all distractions in order to achieve effective teacher performance. To achieve this, the principal should therefore be skilful in management (Udeozor, 2004).

Management is a social process designed to ensure the cooperation, participation, intervention and involvement of others in the effective achievement of a given or predetermined objective. Educational management involves the process of planning and of forecasting, decision-making and formulating educational policies with the aim of attaining set education goals. It involves the application of the process of planning organizing, coordinating, controlling, supervising and evaluating human and material resources with the explicit purpose of achieving educational goals and objectives (Okorji & Unachukwu, 2014). Therefore, the principal as the school manager is at the helm of implementation of education policies. The principal is the person responsible for administrative practices of the school using the resources at his disposal in such a way that the school's objectives are achieved. He performs managerial functions such as planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, communicating and motivating both staff and students towards the realization of both instructional and educational objectives.

In the idea of Fagbamiye (2004), the principal is essentially an organizer and implementer of plans, policies and programmes meant for specific educational objectives. His administrative tasks include directing the teacher and students in an environment conducive to the maximum development of the learner. He plays most

important role in ensuring that excellent teaching occurs in the school through effective managerial practices.

Ajaegbo (2010) posits that in the school system, effective managerial practices involve skilful organization and utilization of resources (human and material) for the achievement of goals. The extent to which the principal discharges his managerial functions to improve teacher effectiveness is a matter of concern, given that most secondary school principals carry enormously varied workload in managing their school resources as well as maintaining their professional leadership status. Likewise, a close observation of the Anambra State Secondary school system shows that the principal's ability to utilize effective managerial practices is an important condition for effective teaching and learning. In the light of this, Bloom, Genakos, Sadan and Van Reena (2012) identified five managerial dimensions which principals should adopt for improving teacher effectiveness in the schools system as; Operational or instructional leadership, supervision, target, human resources management and leadership. The extent to which principals adopt these in enhancing teacher effectiveness appears quite unclear considering the level of teacher effectiveness in the state. However, for the purpose of this study, the focus would be on instructional leadership and supervision as the crux of the discourse. Choosing the two is at the researches' discretion considering the fact that they might be the most critical areas that have direct influence on teachers' effectiveness.

Instructional leadership is associated with measures that a principal takes or delegates to others to enhance students' learning. It includes practices involved in managing both instructions and leadership (Principals' administrative roles) in the school (Ahmad & Hussain, 2015). It is further applicable to best practices directed towards achieving schools' mission and objectives, managing the instructions and promoting positive school learning climate which the school leadership must take into cognizance.

According to Bendikson, Robison and Hattie (2012) principals' instructional leadership practices can be direct (focused on improving teaching) or indirect (focused on creating the conditions for optimal teaching and learning). Direct instructional leadership is focused on the quality of teacher practice itself, whereas indirect instructional leadership is particularly important for secondary school principals because much of the direct leadership is carried out by deputies and heads of departments. It is imperative to recognise that to attain a high level of instructional leadership, requires that the principal must recognise the role of supervisory practices in the system.

The supervisory practices of principals to Obiweluzor, Momoh and Ogbonnaya (2013) involves the art of overseeing the activity of teachers and other educational workers in a school system to ensure that they conform with generally accepted principles and practices of education and the stipulated policies and guidelines of education activity which controls the system of education. Igwe (2001) further stated that the school heads in the bid to supervise, seek to direct, oversee, guide or to make sure that expected standards are met. Thus, school supervision means that the laid down rules, regulations and principles are followed in order to ensure that the minimum standard laid down for the schools are carried out effectively and efficiently. Effective principal supervisory practices are based on identifying certain areas that if well supervised, would help improve quality of secondary education not only in the area of study but in Nigeria as a whole. Similarly, Afolabi and Loto (2008) took into cognizance the following vital areas which needed principal effective supervision to include: Observation of teachers' lesson presentation and lesson plan, teachers' personality and classroom management, teacher-student relationship, and improvising/inspecting reference materials used in instructional delivery.

Apart from the school leadership, teachers are also one of the greatest inputs in any educational system. Describing the role of the teacher in the nation's educational system, the FRN (2013) stated that no education system can rise above the quality of her teachers. Therefore, the quality of any educational system including the secondary education depends largely on the teacher effectiveness. An effective teacher is one who engages all students and provides a learning environment where all students can learn. He works with the resources available to engender high goal attainment within the system. Achieving this fit solely depends on the disposition of the principal in creating a healthy climate through the adoption of effective and efficient managerial practices.

In Anambra State, the level of complacency among teachers, truancy, absenteeism from classes, poor commitment to duty and failure in carrying out instructions from the principal raises a concern as to whether the principals actually apply effective managerial practices in the system. It is thus the drive to appraise principals' managerial practices for teacher effectiveness in secondary school in Anambra State that prompted the study.

2. Statement of the Problem

The issue concerning managerial practices in schools with its concomitant consequences on teacher effectiveness coupled with that of academic performance of students has been a source of great worry to all stakeholders in the education sector. Sule (2013)

observed that most school heads have estranged themselves from the actual instructional realities of the classroom and as a result, their activities as administrative heads seem to be of very little value to both teachers and students. In as much as it is important to appreciate the outstanding performance of secondary school students in Anambra State in the SSCE examinations from 2013 – 2016, there still exists evidences of teachers' failures and laxities in the discharge of their onerous responsibilities. It is therefore worrisome as to whether principals' managerial practices could be responsible for this. This work therefore was determined to appraise principals' managerial practices for teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

2.1 Research Questions

The following two research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do principals adopt instructional leadership practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. To what extent do principals adopt supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

2.2 Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals adopt instructional leadership practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals adopt supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

3. Method

A descriptive survey research design was adopted to appraise principals' managerial practices for teacher effectiveness in secondary schools. The population of the study consists of all the 256 principals and 6396 teachers in the 256 public secondary schools within the six education zones in Anambra State, making a total of 6652. The break down for the 256 secondary schools located within the education zones are; Aguata (47), Awka (61), Nnewi (50), Ogidi (40); Onitsha (32) and Otuocho (26) (source: Department of statistics, post primary schools service commission (PPSSC), Awka, 2017).

The sample for the study is made of 77 principals and 1919 teachers totalling 1996 respondents. This was arrived at by using 30% of the population of principals and

teachers. The use of this percentage was informed by Nworgu (2015), that 30% - 80% of a given population is adequate for research work. Proportionate stratified sampling technique done according zones was used to draw 30% of the total number of principals and teachers in each zone. A 16-item questionnaire titled, "Appraisal of management practices of principals for teacher effectiveness questionnaire (AMPPTTE) was used as the instrument for data collection, the questionnaire has two parts (A & B). Part A sought for background information of the respondents, while part B consisted of 16 items eliciting information from the respondents on the extent of principals' instructional leadership and principals' supervision of teachers for teacher effectiveness. The items on Part B of the instrument were anchored on a four point rating scale of very High Extent (VHE), 4 points, High Extent (HE) 3 points, Low Extent (LE) 2 Points and very Low Extent (VLE) 1 point.

The instrument was validated by two experts from the department of Educational Management and Policy and an expert in measurement and evaluation, all from the faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The experts examined the instrument for relevance in content and clarity of the items. At the end, their suggestions lead to some modifications in the questionnaire before the production of the final version of the instrument.

To ascertain the internal consistency of the instrument, the researchers conducted a pilot test whereby copies of the instrument were administered to 10 principals and 30 teachers, drawn from 10 secondary schools in Enugu State. Thereafter, the data obtained from the test were correlated using Cronbach alpha formula in order to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. This yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.87 and 0.73, summing it up to an overall reliability coefficient of 0.80 and this was considered adequate for the study. The instrument was distributed by the researchers with the help of eight research assistants. The entire 1996 copies of the questionnaire administered were retrieved and used in the analysis. Data obtained were analysed using mean and standard deviation. Any response with a mean score of 2.50 and above was considered as high extent while a mean score below 2.50 was considered as low extent. The z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A hypothesis is significant if z -calculated value is greater than z-critical value; otherwise, the hypothesis is not significant.

4. Results and Findings

Research question 1: To what extent do principals adopt instructional leadership practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean scores of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals adopt instructional leadership practices

S/N	Instructional Leadership Practices	Principals N=77			Teachers N= 1919		
		Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SF	Decision
1.	The principal observes teaching to assess the teaching process	2.90	0.80	HE	2.73	1.04	HE
2.	The principal monitors' students' achievement of lesson content	3.08	0.68	HE	2.81	1.04	HE
3.	The principals encourages peer mentoring among teachers	3.04	0.81	HE	2.74	1.06	HE
4.	The principal uses test scores to make changes in curriculum	3.03	0.87	HE	2.72	1.06	HE
5.	The principal promotes the development of educational goals that reflect societal needs	3.65	0.48	VHE	2.79	1.04	HE
6.	The principal devices effective techniques for helping ineffective teachers.	3.04	0.56	HE	2.87	1.04	HE
7.	The principal displays an awareness and knowledge of recent research about instructional leadership.	2.82	0.94	HE	2.85	1.09	HE
8.	The principal is committed to instructional improvement and stresses this at staff meetings	3.55	0.52	HE	2.82	1.04	HE
Section Mean		3.18	0.78	HE	2.79	1.05	HE

Results presented in table 1 indicated that all the eight items of both the principals and teachers' responses scored above the cut-off mean of 2.20. This showed that both respondents agreed to a high extent with the statement. Also, the section mean of 3.18 and 2.70 of both principals and teachers respectively, indicated that all respondents agreed to a high extent that principals adopt instructional leadership practices for

teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. The overall standard deviation of 0.78 in the principals column and 1.05 in the teachers column, although vary, showing some differences in the scores, but also clustered around the mean scores, indicating homogeneity of the items.

Research Question 2: To what extent do principals adopt supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviation of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals adopt supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra

S/N	Instructional Leadership Practices	Principals N=77			Teachers N= 1919		
		Mean	SD	Decision	Mean	SF	Decision
9.	The principal monitors teachers use of active learning strategies on daily basis.	2.91	0.94	HE	2.64	1.01	HE
10.	The principal supervises how teacher utilize instructional materials in teaching.	3.40	0.63	HE	2.79	1.05	HE
11.	The principal monitors teachers attendance during lessons on daily basis.	3.17	0.59	HE	2.85	1.06	HE
12.	The principal visits classes to observe and help teachers with their teaching problems	3.12	0.87	HE	2.91	0.98	HE
13.	During supervision, principals inform teachers of their teaching in competences right in front of the students.	2.35	1.13	LE	2.65	1.04	HE
14.	The principal involves teachers in planning and executing instructional supervision schedules.	3.58	0.52	VHE	2.78	1.09	HE
15.	The principal supervises teachers'						

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Assessment exercises	2.84	0.68	HE	2.84	1.09	HE
16. The principals delegate teachers' supervision to subject heads.	3.40	0.52	HE	2.84	1.09	HE
Section Mean Score	3.04	0.81	HE	2.77	1.07	HE

Results from table 2 shows that seven items out of eight items of both principals and teachers responses were rated above the cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating that they are the supervisory practices of the principals. Only one item (item 13) scored below the cut-off mean of 2.50 showing that it is the supervisory practices not adopted by the principals. However, the section mean of both principals and teachers of 3.11 and 2.77 respectively are positively in agreement with the items revealing that the extent to which principals adopt supervisory practices for teachers' effectiveness is high.

The standard deviation shows that the responses of principals and teachers rating for each item is slim, suggesting that their responses still clustered, though there is difference in the cluster scores of 0.81 and 1.07 respectively.

Table 3: Z-test analysis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent principals adopt instructional leadership practices for teachers' effectiveness

Group	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree of Freedom	Z-cal	Z-crit
Principals	77	3.18	0.78	1994	3.22	1.96
Teachers	1919	2.79	1.05	1994		

From table 3, the z-calculated of 3.22 is greater than the z-critical value of 1.96, indicating that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals adopt instructional leadership practices for teacher effectiveness. Therefore the null hypotheses of no significant differences is rejected.

Table 4: Z-test analysis of no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which the principals adopt supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness

Group	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree of Freedom	z-cal	z-crit	Dec.
Principals	77	3.11	0.81	1994	2.76	1.96	Significant
Teachers	1919	2.77	1.07				

From table 4, the z-calculated is 2.76 which is greater than the critical value of 1.96. This indicates that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which principals adopt supervisory practices for teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State.

5. Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that the principals to a high extent adopted the instructional leadership practices for teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Collaborating with this view Oyetunji (2006) opined that there is a great influence between school heads' leadership styles and teacher effectiveness. Expatiating this fact, Oyetunji noted that the principals' leadership behaviour for example, his/her expectations, values, beliefs, relationship with teachers among others help to shape the climate of the school as envisaged. Mendel (2012), suggests that there is a major reason for the attention being paid to principals, which is the emergence of research that has found an empirical link between school instructional leadership and students' achievement led by teacher effectiveness. As postulated by Wallace (2012) effective leaders should emphasize research-based strategies to improve teaching and learning and initiate discussions about instructional approaches both in teams and with individual teachers. Mendels further highlighted that principals who are effective instructional leaders ripples through classroom in order to boost teacher effectiveness for school learning. Here effective leadership begins with the development of a school wide vision of commitment to high standards and the success of all teachers and students. It seemingly implies that principals as instructional leaders usually specifies the school aims, organizes the instructional programme in order to achieve these goals and see that teachers work to achieve the goals for students positive performance, less wonders the positive result of the study.

The test of null hypothesis is significant suggesting that there is a variation in the ratings of principals and teachers on the principals' instructional leadership practices for teachers' effectiveness. However, this difference might be burn out of the feeling that teachers could see the principal's action to carry out effective instructional leadership at all cost as jeopardizing their free will to work at their own pace.

Moreover, the study also revealed that the principals to a high extent adopt supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Anambra State. The implication is that all the supervisory practices including monitoring of teachers, supervision of the teachers' utilization of instructional materials, teacher attendance to class among others are adopted by the principals to a high extent in order to enhance teacher effectiveness. This finding is in tandem with the view of Wallace (2012) who appreciates that principals spend time in classrooms to evaluate instruction and make close observations of what is working and what is not and then make sure to discuss what they have found with teachers. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) Principals' supervision is meant to ensure quality control through a continuous monitoring of instruction. Supporting this view, Ogunu (2000) enthuses that principals supervises the teachers and other workers in the school system to ensure that they conform to general acceptable principles and standards of education so as to achieve the goals of education. It therefore goes to say that no matter how proficient teachers are, they are deemed to be supervised aimed at providing students with quality learning. Also principals supervise and monitor the work and behaviour of teachers in order to improve individual teacher's competences that could position them for effective teaching outcome.

One possible explanation why principals adopt supervisory practices in line with the finding could be as a result of regular payment of salaries to principals and teachers in secondary schools in the State. Consequently, they leave no stone unturned to justify the motivation by implicitly performing their supervisory responsibilities without fear or favour. The test of null hypothesis indicates a significant difference in the ratings of principals and teachers. The reason for this finding might be in relation to MacGregor's theory 'X' that workers dislike to work and can avoid it if possible. The implication is that teachers may not be enjoying principals' constant close matching in terms of monitoring hence the significant difference in their rating with the principals.

6. Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that principals in public secondary schools in Anambra State adopt managerial practices in the areas of instructional leadership and

supervisory practices for teacher effectiveness. Therefore it can be concluded that adopting these practices lead to teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools which invariably translates to the achievement of the objectives of secondary education not only in Anambra State but also in Nigeria in general. It is therefore not surprising why Anambra State has been performing very outstandingly well, most often taken the first position in secondary school certificate examinations from 2013/2014 to 2015/2016 academic years. This is an epitome of teacher's effectiveness resulting from principals' instructional leadership and supervisory practices in secondary schools.

7. Recommendations

1. Since the principals demonstrate effective utilization of instructional leadership practices for teachers' effectiveness resulting in students' outstanding performance in external examinations, the state government should continue to encourage this by regularly sponsoring the principals to continuous professional development training on various managerial practices. This is to keep them abreast with current managerial developments so as to always give the teachers needed management support for effective teaching.
2. Principals should intensify effort in their adoption of supervisory practices so that teachers would always be on their toes to ensure that the objectives of secondary education are consistently achieved.

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